

VETERINARY SCIENCES

REGIONALIZATION OF SHEEP BREEDS IN AZERBAIJAN AND INNOVATIVE WAYS OF HORMONAL POLYOVLUTION

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Abstract

The article investigates the intensive development of the sheep breeding farms of the republic, their mating campaigns and their peculiarities. Also, a month before the ram rush, the hormones of melatonin and progesterone were added to the powder of barley and corn in the powder form, and the percentage of motivation and puppies was studied.

At the same time, specific features of Balbas breeds and their mating campaign was also analyzed.

Keywords: regionalization, exterior, rational feeding, infections, congenital company, selection, breed, adapted.

Developing reproductive and feeding strategies under the project "Sustainable Sheep Development and Creating a Value Chain for Food Production" funded by the Government of Azerbaijan and implemented in December 2018 under the FAO-Azerbaijan Partnership Program. sustainable development of the value chain is intended as a goal.

Specific characteristics of local (local) sheep breeds should be analyzed and taken into account during regionalization in order to ensure and regulate sustainable, sustainable, rational development of sheep breeding in the Republic. Many sheep breeds should be studied with unique features and their adaptation (genetic resistance to diseases, adaptation to abrupt climate

change, high calving, etc.). Thus, sheep are easily adapted to the influence of environmental factors in geographically diverse areas. Strong control over genetic biodiversity of sheep and the establishment of a proper management system provide a great guarantee for global food security, the needs of the population for food products, as well as other raw materials (fur, wool, puppies, etc.). Thus, Balbas breeds in Nakhchivan AR, Ganja and Gazakh regions of Bozakh breed, Gadabay and Shamkir regions of Azerbaijan Mountain Merino, Absheron peninsula and Gala rocks, Agjabadi of Karadlak, Lankaran It would be more desirable for breeding of Karabakh, Lezgi and Herik breeds in Sheki-Zagatala and Kur-Araz regions.

According to the sex zoning plan, the Balbas breed, widely cultivated and purified in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, is white, with black spots around the eyes, ears and feet, below the glass. According to productivity indicators, Balbas sheep are still cultivated in the South Caucasus region, including the best breeds of sheep, meat, dairy and dairy. Balbas sheep is hornless, wool is of high quality and milk is fat. Sheep live weight is 55 kg and rams weigh more than 65 kg. The fat content in the tail is 6-7 kg in rams and 4-5 kg in the main sheep, and the wool is white and sufficiently long, 12-17 cm long. Sheep weighs 3-4 kg and 2.5-2.8 kg in sheep. The wool of lamb sheep is highly valued in weaving, especially carpet weaving. Milk productivity of fattening sheep is higher than that of other local sheep breeds. Fatty sheep give 70-75 kg of milk during lactation. This breed was created as a result of folk selection. Nails have long, well-developed joints, and nails are strong. Therefore, these sheep can travel about 18-20 km a day during the migration and can graze on the slopes. In well-fed flocks, the live weight of mother sheep is 60-70 kg, and the live weight of rams is 80-88 kg, sometimes 100-110 kg. The characteristics of feral sheep are very high. Therefore, it is advisable to regionalize this genus in the Autonomous Republic in accordance with the biological and economic characteristics of this genus.

The research was conducted mainly on the experimental animals kept in the subsidiary production practice of Araz Scientific Production Association named after academician Hasan Aliyev in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and in the Shakhbuz district support station. In the experiment used 40 head of Balbas breed sheep. The studies analyzed the specific characteristics of Balbas breeds of sheep kept in sheep farms of different regions of the autonomous republic and their mating campaign. In order to organize the mating campaign, a month before the ramming, sheep were given parchment and barley and cornmeal, along with melatonin and progesterone hormones. As a result, the sheep show a desire to escape at the same time, and the fat sheep give birth at the same time. Because of the high number of eggs in the mother sheep, which are used for hormone melatonin and progesterone, the number of twin lambs born during calving also increases. We have learned about mating campaigns in sheep breeds and their breeding characteristics. For this purpose, one month prior to slaughter, sheep were divided into 4 groups and fed in four forms: A (usual feeding - control group), B (intensive feeding - group 1), C (mixed feed from barley, sorghum and corn - group 2), D (meltingin and progesterone hormone supplementation in powdered barley and corn sprout - group 3).

Materials and methods of research

Diagram. Feeding in groups of ewes one month before the lambing

During the analysis of the research and experiments, motivation and calving in the sheep fed different

feeding norms in the Araz Research and Production Association subsidiary farm (**Table**):

Table. Motivation and calving in maternal sheep fed with different feed norms

Nº	Group	Number of practice sheep	One month before feeding	Motivation (with-%)	Childbirth	Live weight in lambs (kg)
1	A-control	10	Usual feeding	70	80	2,5-2,8
2	B-1	10	Intensive feeding	80	90	2,6-3,0
3	C-2	10	Mixed feed: barley, sorghum, corn	90	110	2,0-2,7
44	D-3	10	Mixed fodder: melatonin, progesterone, barley, corn starch	100	140	1,8-2,5

Newborn lambs, active in control A-group, 2.5-2.8 kg, weaning -80%; B - live weight of lambs born in the 1st group is 2.6-3.0 kg, weaning -90%, C - average weight of lambs born in the 2nd group is 2,0-2,7 kg,

weaning - 110%, D - average live weight of lambs in the 3rd group was less than 1.8 - 2.5 kg compared to the twin lambs and weighed 140%.

Chart. Percentage of breeding in domestic sheep

Apparently, one month before the start of the mating campaign, 120-140 heads of baby sheeps can be obtained from one hundred head sheep per month if the mother sheep are given melatonin and progesterone hormones along with barley and corn starch. Sheep reaches puberty of 8-9 months, but it is advisable to carry out the first pair at 12-18 months. In sheep, the sex cycle is on average 17 days, stimulation is 24 hours, duration of throat is 145-150 days. Sheep breeds belong to short-days animals, that is, they have sexual activity in the autumn and short of the day. Different types of mating are used during this time. In a freely pairing, rams are freely driven in the sheep flock. (for every ram there are 20-25 mother sheep). Although this type of mating is simple, it requires a lot of rams. During manual pairing, the test rams are released into the herd, and the willing sheep are identified and paired on a special bench. In this pairing, one ram holds 60-80 head sheep. Artificial insemination allows you to make extensive use of the most valuable producer. During artificial insemination, 300-400 heads of sheep are fertilized with

one ram's seed. Thanks to such measures the sheep show a desire to escape at the same time, and the fat sheep give birth at the same time. Normal calving usually takes about 30-40 minutes. As soon as the lamb is born, its mouth must be cleaned. After the mother licked and dried baby sheep, the the person who controls the fetus must feed the baby sheep. It is important that the lamb be fed with breast milk. In the absence of milk in the sheep, the lamb eats eggs yolk or the milk of another sheep that gave born at the same time. Contains the ability to function in the oral milk, which regulates the stomach and intestines of the lamb. Oral milk increases resistance to the body and prevents infections as well as gastrointestinal diseases. The giving birth sheep, were kept in the sheepfold for 2-3 days with a lamb. Also, the sheep 6-7 days are not allowed in the herd. Birth in sheep breeding takes place in winter and autumn. For winter lambing, having a sufficient forage base, lambs with high survival rate and productivity are born in warm pastures. Lambs born in winter eat quality food. Each lamb should be fed at least 0.6-0.7 kg of dry

grass and mixed feeds (compound feed) per day. One lamb is given 5-7 grams of granulated salt per day. In addition, the salt is added to the stable (lick salt).

Result. 1. Zoning of sheep breeds in the republic should be carried out in accordance with the regional zoning plan.

2. In order to organize the mating campaign, it is advisable to give the sheep a month before the start, with the addition of barley and cornflour, as well as melatonin and progesterone hormones.

3. On the sunny days in winter, the pregnant sheep should be allowed to go outdoors every day. This has a positive effect on the health of the sheep, the easy birth and the normal development of the baby.

4. Feeding of sheep should be properly compiled and feed rate for sheep kept in pasture conditions should be increased by 15-20%. The wintering period should be 70% in the diet, 20% in grains, 8% in juicy fodder and 2% in mineral feed supplements.

5. External environmental factors have a negative effect on the body of the sheep in the cold or extreme heat of the breed and the extreme heat, the change of air, and the presence of bilateral air currents in the stall. The temperature in the stove should be 10-120° C, and 150° C where baby lambs are stored. In the winter, the stables should be kept dry, at normal heat and clean.

6. Two weeks before the birth, the mother sheep should be selected, grazed under the supervision of experienced shepherds, as well as cared for, fed, cleaned

and other processes must be conducted at the same time every day according to their working hours.

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